

A PARAMETRIC STUDY TO DETERMINE THE INFLUENCE OF GEOMETRIC VARIATIONS ON THE PERFORMANCE OF A BULKHEAD TO SHELL PLATING JOINT

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with the design of Tee connections in FRP ships and boats. A brief review of the problem is presented and a reference is made to current design procedure. Design variables most influencing joint behaviour are identified and the manner in which the finite element analysis models are generated is then discussed. Finally the results of a systematically varied set of designs are compared from a failure viewpoint and the influence of the critical parameters is highlighted.

Keywords: composite materials; bonded joints; design; tee connections; joint geometry; material properties; finite element modelling.

1. INTRODUCTION

FRP structures are especially prone to failure at bonded connections. The weakness in this context is caused by the absence of load bearing fibres across bonded surfaces, by the relatively thin adhesive layer forming the bond, and through the occurrence of stress concentrations associated with joint geometry and production considerations. Lack of bond ductility and the absence of crack-arresting action by fibres can result in a rapid propagation of small regions of debonding by a "peeling" action until catastrophic failure occurs.

The connections could be entirely bonded or may be reinforced by the use of metal fasteners such as bolts, screws or rivets. Use of fasteners in ships is not very cost efficient and hence this practice is relatively uncommon. Because of this lack of redundancy in attachments, special care needs to be exercised when dealing with major structural connections. In ships, the connections could refer to:

- a) butt joints which may be required between prefabricated deck panels;
- b) intersections between longitudinal and transverse stiffeners;
- c) linking deck edge with shell; or
- d) joining bulkheads to deck or shell.

In a design context, much progress has been made with regard to the overall hull structure. However, apart from some testing and analysis in the early days of GRP ship building, relatively little attention has been paid to the design of joint details. Whilst the resulting joints have fully met stringent design requirements which, in warships, may require underwater shock loadings, there is much scope for better understanding of joint behaviour, leading to more cost and performance-efficient designs.

In the early days of GRP shipbuilding some testing and analyses of these joints were carried out, and this formed the basis of current design practices. More recently work has centred on determining the key design characteristics that affect joint performance, using both experimental, and detailed analytical studies. This work resulted in a "new" design of joint being developed whose characteristics directly opposed the current design principles.

The object of this paper is to study the behaviour of this new design of Tee connection by parametrically varying these key geometric features to determine their influence on the joints performance.

2. DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

The primary function of a Tee joint is to transmit flexural, tensile and shear loads between two sets of panels meeting at the joint. The joint itself is formed by laminating strips of reinforcing cloth (or overlaminates) either side of the joint to form a double (or boundary) angle connection. The load transmission is done entirely through the cloth-resin plies and any filleting resin within the boundary angle. The details of the cloth plies and resin therefore need careful attention in order to ensure the joint is strong enough to resist the applied loads.

Such careful and explicit modelling of joint geometry and material makeup is not allowed for by currently available design synthesis methods. One of the earliest approaches to GRP structure design is outlined in the Gibbs and Cox manual (1) where it is stated that the dimensions of the boundary angle "should be consistent with strength requirements"; specific procedures concerning joint design, however, are not elaborated. Current naval standards (2) prescribe the thickness of the boundary angle to be at least half (and preferably two-thirds) the thickness of the thinnest member meeting at the joint. Flange layup dimensions, the layup and stacking sequence are also specified. A typical arrangement is shown in Figure 1A. Again no design requirements or modelling procedures are laid down.

With regard to current merchant marine and small craft practice, design guidance is sought primarily from classification society rules. Lloyd's rules (3) state that "the scantlings are to be determined by direct calculation". Guidance is provided with regard to layup and stacking sequence. In the rules of the American Bureau of Shipping (4), boundary angle thickness is again given as a function of the thickness of members meeting at the joint. Det Norske Veritas (5) has no formulae for direct derivation of scantlings but offers tables of loadings, allowable material properties and maximum/limiting stresses from which the boundary angle details are to be determined. As before, no modelling preference is specified.

Arguably the most comprehensive efforts towards understanding joint behaviour have been in the field of naval minehunter design. Early efforts (6-7) were targetted towards mechanically fastened joints. However, primarily because of cost considerations, later developmental research (8-9) concentrated upon replacing bolted connections with bonded ones. The thrust of these studies was also of a practical and developmental nature. The studies were targetted towards specific

applications and hence broader conclusions towards general usage are difficult to extract.

On a broader front, attempts at studying joint behaviour have been on the basis of some limited testing backed up by more detailed finite element studies (10–11). The test programme for this type of joint was devised to study the influence of the most critical variables:

- a) Fillet radius,
- b) Number of plies in the boundary angle,
- c) Material make-up of the boundary angle plies,
- d) Edge gap between the web and flange of the tee, and
- e) Shape of the edge of the wedge.

The variations were compared with "standard", current practice. The test specimens were subjected to a displacement-controlled pull-off of the web at 45 degrees to the base (flange) plate and restrained as shown in Figure 2. The full details of the test programme have been reported elsewhere (11). The major conclusion that emerged from the tests was that a joint comprising a large fillet radius with a thin overlamine was "better" than the traditional joint with a small fillet radius and thick overlamine – see Figure 1. This is evidenced from the load-deflection curves for the two joints as shown in Figure 3.

This practical study was supported by detailed numerical studies (12). The focus of these early models was to examine stress regimes within the joint particularly with respect to quantifying failure within the joint and to derive a measure for joint efficiency. Some general features of joint response vis-a-vis geometry and material variations were also noted. This work illustrated the load paths within the different joint designs, supporting the observed failure modes seen during experimentation. However, no attempt was made at studying designs with a systematically varied set of parameters. That is the main subject of this current paper.

3. MODELLING CONSIDERATIONS

The numerical analysis was performed using the ANSYS finite element analysis package (13). This has a composite capability in that it provides options from three layered elements, comprising two eight-noded shell and one eight-noded solid. The geometry of the boundary angle problem precludes the use of shell elements as some stacking is required, so the 3D solid element is used throughout. This element is defined by eight nodes, each having three degrees of freedom (translations in the nodal x, y, and z directions), and has large deflection and stress stiffening capabilities. The flexible resin fillet was represented using an isoparametric 3D solid element with large deflection and plasticity capabilities.

Several preliminary analyses were conducted to assess the effects of incorporating these capabilities, and also the effect of varying the mesh density. Memory and wavefront considerations apply an upper limit to this but nevertheless a reasonably high level of definition was achieved. Models were developed with a consistent mesh density so that any mesh density effects are eliminated from the parametric results. These were run using the large deflection option.

The material properties used were derived from manufacturers data (where this was available), from experimental results and by interpolation from properties of similar materials. This last method was necessary since for some materials there was no data available and the nature of the material made the manufacture of test coupons very difficult. Nevertheless the derived properties have been

shown to provide good correlation with experimental results (12). The properties used are listed in Table 1. The properties of the fillet material are nonlinear and incorporate very large plastic deformation before failure, making it necessary to apply the load incrementally to follow this plasticity. Iterative solutions were completed using 10 iterations per load step and 15 load steps. A convergence criterion was applied to each iteration to prevent excessive processing. Convergence was usually found to occur after between 4 and 8 iterations depending on the model and the loadstep.

The models were restrained as shown in Figure 2, to represent the clamping arrangement used during experimentation. This loading condition was developed to represent a boundary angle subjected to both a tensile pull-off and sideload, as would occur within a tank structure.

4. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The basis models from which all the following results have been derived have been shown previously (12) to give reasonable correlation with experimental results. Experimental results are not available for most of the wide range of geometries considered here, but it has been assumed, with reasonable confidence, that the consistency maintained across the models will ensure the validity of the comparative results.

Results are given for the three most significant variables, that is fillet radius, overlamine thickness and gap size (see Figure 4). Fillet radius has been used as the "base" variable since it has the greatest effect on joint performance, and is the best representation of scale, allowing the results to be interperated for other applications. Results are given in terms of overall deflection, maximum stress in the fillet, maximum overlamine in-plane stress, and maximum overlamine through-thickness stress, for a constant load (in this case 12.5 kN, chosen as it is intermediary between the experimental failure load of the current and new joint designs). The results need to be examined in context of joint efficiency (12). The aim of efficient joint design is to ensure that all the above stresses reach their maximum values at the same applied load. Traditionally this has not been possible as overlamine through-thickness stresses have been excessive in thick overlaminates long before in-plane and fillet stresses have developed, resulting in premature delaminations occurring in the root of the boundary angle.

Firstly, consider Figure 5, the results for the variation in overlamine thickness and fillet radius. The gap size is constant at 20mm. Several points can be seen:

1. Overall deflections decrease considerably with increasing overlamine thickness and fillet radius. Since in the Tee-joint almost all of the overall deflection occurs in the joint region this would be expected to have a significant effect on the internal stress distributions within the joint
2. When the radius is small the stress in the fillet reduces as overlamine thickness increases. As fillet radius increases, however, the fillet stress becomes almost independent of overlamine thickness and fillet radius, indicating that overlaminations of more than four layers, and fillet radii greater than 75mm, have little effect on fillet stress. However, fillet radii smaller than this should be avoided as the fillet stress rises rapidly as the radius is reduced.
3. The in-plane stress in the overlamine reduces rapidly as overlamine thickness and fillet radius are increased from small values. However, as both these variables increase further their effect is reduced, indicating a diminishing return for the increased joint size.

4. For all but the smallest fillet radius, the overlamine through-thickness stress increases with increasing overlamine thickness. This increase, whilst appearing small in the figure due to the inordinately high values for the 25mm fillet radius, is very significant when failure, for a typical polyester resin/woven roving laminate, will occur at 8–11 MPa (14). The very high stress levels in the 25mm fillet radius models, both in the fillet and the overlamine, indicate that the joint would have failed long before this level of applied load was reached.

Next consider Figure 6, the results for varying gap size and fillet radius. Overlamine thickness is constant at 2 layers of woven rovings. Gap size is a significant variable in as much as in the production of large structures it is difficult to control, thus its effect on the joint performance need to be determined. The results are given in the same format as above, for the same applied load. Significant points are:

1. Gap size has no effect on overall deflections or stresses in the overlamine, and the effect of radius remains as before.
2. The stress in the fillet rises as gap size increases, but this effect is reduced as fillet radius increases, such that for radii greater than 75mm gap size has little effect up to 20mm. Large gap sizes result in high fillet stresses in all but the largest fillet radii.
3. The very high stresses associated with the smallest radius above are also evident here.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The above results show clearly the effects of the different design variables considered. The benefits of large radii are to reduce stresses in all areas, albeit with diminishing returns in some areas, whilst reducing overlamine thickness reduces its through-thickness stresses, thus preventing premature delamination. This is in direct contrast to current practice. This decrease in overlamine thickness also leads to increased flexibility, which reduces the effects of the "hard spot" the joint can create in the overall structure, but also leads to increased overlamine in-plane stresses and fillet stresses, so clearly a compromise needs to be achieved.

Generally the results of this work have shown that the new design of Tee-joint is a favourable alternative to the current practice. Past results have indicated that a suitably refined joint can exceed the ultimate load carrying capacity of the current design by 150%, without being prone to premature delaminations in the overlamine. This is achieved with a weight reduction of 60%, and, along with the potentially considerable savings in production costs, should ensure its further consideration.

With the exceptions noted in the discussion of results above, the "production" variable (gap size) has a limited effect on the performance of the joint. However, Large gaps, greater than a quarter of the fillet radius, should be avoided to prevent excessive fillet stresses. Fillet radius and overlamine thickness have significant effects on joint behaviour and can be optimised for a given application.

The graphs included in this paper can be used as a basis for a design optimisation procedure providing that the relevant failure information exists for the materials used.

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Figure 1. Geometries and Features of Tee Joints.

Figure 2. Boundary Conditions Applied to Tee Joint Models.

Figure 3. Comparison of Load/Deflection Curves for Current and New Designs of Tee Joints.

Figure 4. Tee Joint Design Variables.

Material	E (GPa)	ν	Gxy (GPa)	UTS (MPa)	Failure Strain (%)
Polyester	3.2	-	-	58	6
* CR1152	0.5	-	-	26	100
+ CR1200	0.7	-	-	32	27
Polyester/WR					
Warp	14.68	0.123	3.09	207	1.4
Weft	13.06	0.139	3.09	207	1.4
Interlaminar	-	-	-	12.2	
Polyester/CSM					
Inplane	6.89	0.13	3.45	-	
Interlaminar	-	-	-	11.2	
CR1200/WR					
Warp	6.375	-	-	183.3	2.8
Weft	3.926	-	-	188.9	4.8
CR1200/CSM					
Inplane	3.023	-	-	110.4	3.6

* CR1152 = Urethane Acrylate Resin.
 + CR1200 = Polyester/Urethane Acrylate mix.

Table 1: Material Properties used in F.E. Analysis.

Effect of Overlamine on Deflection.

Effect of Overlamine on Stress in Fillet.

Effect of Overlamine on its In-plane Stress

Effect of Overlamine on its T-T Stress

Figure 5. Results for Variations in Overlamine Thickness.

Effect of Gap Size on Deflection

Effect of Gap Size on Stress in Fillet

Effect of Gap Size on Overlamine In-plane Stress

Effect of Gap Size on Overlamine T-T Stress

Figure 6. Results for Variations in Gap Size.